

Model the Effect Community Trust, Financial Organizational, Leadership on Organizational Performance: Empiric Study in Boarding Schools

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to prove whether from each variable there is an influence with independent variables with data processing in the object of research. This study used a survey method. The population in this study is the Head of Boarding Schools (Mudir) in West Java domestic as many as 56 Heads of Islamic Boarding Schools (Mudir), with purposive Sampling and data Analysis Techniques using simple regression analysis assisted by SPSS version 24. variability of community trust with Organizational Performance has a significant influence, the third test with the results that financial organization has a significant influence on Organizational Performance, Leadership with Organizational Performance has a significant influence, and testing together found that 58.8% is significant and positive. The results of this study are just the beginning and can be continued in other studies added with other variables with the same or other objects.

INTRODUCTION

Public trust is the foundation of solid organizational performance. Trust is a key aspect that influences the relationship between the organization and external stakeholders. When society has high trust in an organization, it creates a positive environment that has a big impact (Fricker Jr et al., 2014; Mayer et al., 1995) People who believe in an organization are more likely to give their financial support, time, and resources (Drevs et al., 2014);(Wenny Desty Febrian.S.E.M.M | Rini Ardista et al., 2022) Strong trust can help organizations build a strong reputation, which is a valuable asset in attracting necessary financing and partnerships.

According to (Gazimova et al., 2019; Roberts & Dowling, 2002) Strong trust can help organizations build a strong reputation, which is a valuable asset in attracting necessary financing and partnerships. Organizational financing is the foundation for operational continuity, according to (Drnevich & Croson, 2013) a stable source of financing enables organizations to implement long-term strategies and better achieve goals. Organizations that have sufficient financing can plan for innovation and long-term investments that support growth, consistent financing allows organizations to run programs and projects well, which can create greater impact (Hitt et al., 2019)

Effective leadership is key to maximizing an organization's potential. A leader who is able to motivate the team, take strategic decisions, and lead the organization towards a clear vision is a valuable asset (Northouse, 2021). Clear leadership gives strong direction to the organization and its team, helping them understand long-term goals, Leaders who are able to motivate team members create a productive and innovative work culture. Wise leadership in taking strategic decisions helps organizations avoid mistakes that can interfere with performance (Ruben & Gigliotti, 2017; SEO et al., 2012)

According to (Mukhtar & Prasetyo, 2020) Boarding school, as traditional Islamic educational institutions in Indonesia, are also influenced by factors such as community trust, organizational financing, and leadership in achieving optimal performance. People who trust pesantren tend to provide support in various forms, including donations, participation in pesantren programs, and the selection of pesantren as a place of education for their children. Islamic boarding schools that have strong sources of financing can more easily plan innovations in curriculum, improve facilities, and provide training for teachers (Afiah, 2022) Pesantren leaders must be able to provide clear direction to teachers and students, motivate them to achieve educational goals, and make strategic decisions that support the growth of boarding schools (Safira, 2021)

Community trust can increase sources of financing, and wise leadership can utilize these resources to improve the performance of boarding school. Effective management of all three factors can help pesantren achieve their educational and social goals better. Currently pesantren are experiencing an increase and demand about religious educational institutions, this phenomenon reflects an increase in demand from the public for religious education and pesantren as institutions that offer more in-depth Islamic religious education, Many pesantren are currently experiencing a phenomenon where students

come from various social, economic, and geographical backgrounds, which shows the inclusivity of pesantren. Gaps seen from the above phenomena and theories Financing gaps can arise when pesantren have limited financial resources, which can affect their ability to provide adequate educational facilities and programs, and this gap is related to teaching quality and teacher competence, especially in terms of innovative and effective teaching.

The purpose of this study is to prove whether from each variable there is an influence with independent variables with data processing in the object of research.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Community Trust

According (Jachimowicz et al., 2017) Community trust refers to the level of trust that individuals have in their communities and institutions. This can have an impact on many aspects of people's lives, including health services. In one study that states about community trust is skepticism that health care providers, systems, and researchers in marginalized communities still exist and are complex. This highlights the importance of understanding the direct experiences of community members and the mechanisms that maintain this mistrust (Hooper et al., 2019)

Community life plays an important role in encouraging volunteerism and cooperation for the betterment of society. In addition, trust in local government is associated with a higher likelihood of volunteering in local initiatives. Interestingly, when people have high trust in their local government, their participation in regional public meetings decreases (Mulaphong, 2023)

Financial Organizational

According (Rekunen et al., 2020) Financial management refers to the organization and management of financial resources within a community. includes strategic coordination, organizing, leadership and controlling financial activities aimed at achieving organizational goals and objectives. The tasks of a financial organization include preparing budgets, preparing financial statements, analyzing financial data, and making financial choices. The composition of a financial organization can vary depending on the scale and complexity of the organization. Generally, the framework of a financial organization includes a finance department or department entrusted with managing the financial resources of the organization (Aldoseri et al., 2022)

The finance department is headed by a chief financial officer (CFO), who oversees financial transactions and communicates with the organization's senior management. The role of the financial manager is to ensure financial stability and expansion of the organization by mitigating financial risks, developing financial strategies and providing financial advice to organizational management (Antunes et al., 2017)

Leadership

According (Marie, 2015) Leadership can be described as the ability to motivate and influence others to achieve common goals or objectives.

Democratic leadership is a leadership style in which the leader prioritizes cooperation among group members in solving problems and obtaining their consent before taking action (Bell, 2015b) Authoritative leadership is a leadership style in which the leader controls the entire decision-making, gives orders, and delegates responsibilities without soliciting input from team members (Bell, 2015a)

Successful leadership requires a combination of skills that include communication, decision-making, problem-solving, and emotional intelligence. A skilled leader is able to inspire and inflame the spirit in his team while providing direction and guidance to help them achieve goals (Hoxha & Heimerer, 2019).

Leadership can influence subordinates to work productively and a dynamic work culture, successful leadership will bring career success to subordinates and the Company. In line with research from (Susanto, Ali, et al., 2023);(Susanto, Widyastuti, et al., 2023);(Susanto, Agusinta, et al., 2023);(Susanto, Syailendra, et al., 2023);(Candra Susanto & Nyoman Sawitri, 2023);(Siagian et al., 2023);(Sawitri et al., 2019);(Bratha et al., 2023);(Adiguzel et al., 2020);(Burns et al., 2015).

Organizational Performance

Organizational effectiveness refers to the ability of an organization to achieve its goals effectively and efficiently. This can be influenced by many factors such as leadership style, organizational culture, total quality management, performance management practices and dynamic capabilities (Mohammed & Al - Abrow, 2022; Ong & Tan, 2022). The use of modern management methods, such as transformational management and empowerment, can have a positive impact on organizational effectiveness (Mohammed & Al - Abrow, 2022).

The application of total quality management techniques has the potential to improve operational efficiency and contribute to the improvement of organizational culture. In addition, the use of performance management practices, which include quality and internal management methods, can provide positive results to organizational performance (Gomes & Mendes, 2022).

Hypotheses Development

Relationship Community Trust and Organizational Performance

Studies (Yan et al., 2022)(Dipaola & Guy, 2009)(Dipaola & Guy, 2009)

The results of the study suggested social capital was associated with improved regional emergency services by examining its relationship with the performance of ambulance trusts in England. The study found that social capital, which includes measures of people's organizational lives, political effectiveness, and social trust, is associated with regional crisis recovery. Taken together, these findings suggest that public trust can positively impact organizational performance and organizations can benefit from investing in initiatives that encourage trust and social capital.

H_1 : *Community Trust has positive and significant on Organizational Performance.*

Relationship Financial Organizational and Organizational Performance

In the context of Pesantren, discussions about financial resources and organizational performance hold significant importance. Financial resources are essential to ensure the seamless operation of the institution and to deliver high-quality education to students, the results of research at Pesantren Nurul Muhibbi on the process of financial management in Tanah Laut concluded that financial planning, implementation, control and reporting are important aspects of financial management (Khofi et al., 2021). A study on the implementation of spiritual and financial responsibility in pesantren found that financial responsibility is important to maintain and maintain pesantren (Wati et al., 2022)

The managerial, financial resources and performance of the organization concludes that the competence of the management responsible for financial resources is important in the interaction between funding and performance. Therefore, it is important for Pesantren to have effective financial management processes and responsible financial practices to ensure organizational effectiveness (Flink & Chen, 2021).

H_2 : *Financial Organizational has positive and significant on Organizational Performance*

Relationship Leadership on Organizational Performance

Based on the findings of the search, several studies have examined the influence of leadership on organizational performance within Pesantren, research results with studies from (Wiyono, 2021) communication and trust have a significant effect on team performance in Waqf Drinking Water Management at Riyadlul Jannah Pacet Islamic Boarding School Mojokerto. Another study from (Tamam & Farihin, 2020) leadership training management in Islamic boarding schools with a focus on planning, organizing, implementing and supervising the management of leadership training centers.

Research results from (Hosaini, 2015; Mu'azzomi et al., 2017) stated the relationship between management and organizational culture in Islamic boarding schools and how to develop employee commitment and satisfaction in the organization. Together, these studies show that leadership plays an important role in interns' organizational performance.

H_3 : *Financial Organizational has positive and significant on Organizational Performance*

After explaining the relationship between variables and hypotheses, The proposed framework image is as follows;

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

This study used a survey method. The purpose of the survey method is to collect information about respondents' choices through structured questionnaires (Sekaran, 2010). The methods used are limited to descriptive research or samples that test pre-established hypotheses (Vogt, 2015). Testing the proposed hypothesis involves the use of statistical expressions or structural models suitable for cause-and-effect analysis. Therefore, the method used in this study is a quantitative approach with correlational research, which is a type of research that aims to find out whether there is a relationship between several variables (Cooper and Schlinder, 2006).

The population in this study is the Head of Pesantren (Mudir) in West Java domestic as many as 56 Heads of Islamic Boarding Schools (Mudir), with purposive Sampling, Data Analysis Techniques using simple regression analysis assisted by SPSS version 24.

RESULTS

The validity test through SPSS.24 was obtained from all 56 statements given to all respondents who were filled in through questionnaire sheets and processed data, all statements from Community Trust variables were declared valid and could be processed further.

Table 1. Uji Validitas Variabel Community Trust

COMMUNITY TRUST		
N	Valid	56
	Missing	0

In the frequency test process through SPSS V.21, a standard deviation frequency test was carried out to obtain the percentage of validity and cumulative percentage stating that the results of the Financial Organizational independent variable were very satisfactory.

Table 2. Uji Validitas Variabel Financial Organizational

N	Valid	56
	Missing	0

In the frequency test process through SPSS V.21, a standard deviation frequency test was carried out to obtain the percentage of validity and cumulative percentage stating that the results of the independent Leadership variable were very satisfactory.

Table 3. Uji Validitas Variabel Performance Organizational

Statistics		
PERFORMANCE ORGANIZATION		
N	Valid	56
	Missing	0

Regression

Table 4. Regresion

Model summary		
R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.172	.124	.588
a. Predictors: (Constant), LEADERSHIP, FINANCING ORGANIZATION, COMMUNITY TRUST		

Based on the summary model table above, the R Square number is 0.588 or (58.8.3%). This shows that the independent variables Community Trust (X1), Financial Organizational (X2), Leadership were able to increase the dependent variable of employee attachment (Y) by 58.8%.

Table 5. Anova

df	Mean Square	F
3	1.244	3.596
52	.346	
55		
a. Dependent Variable: PERFORMANCE ORGANIZATION		
b. Predictors: (Constant), LEADERSHIP, FINANCING ORGANIZATION, COMMUNITY TRUST		

From the data above, $F_{\text{calculate}} = 3.596$, $F_{\text{table}} = 3.46$, $F_{\text{calculate}} > F_{\text{table}}$, then H_0 is rejected meaning there is a difference between Community Trust and Organizational Performance, significance level is 0.05, Significance of test results $p = (0.000 < 0.05)$, then H_0 is rejected meaning there is a difference between Community Trust, Financial Organizational, Leadership and Organizational Performance.

Table 6. Coefficient
Coefficient^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.588	1.014		1.566	.123
Community Trust	.383	.130	.383	2.937	.005
Financing Organization	.017	.135	.016	.126	.901
Leadership	.235	.141	.214	1.672	.101

a. Dependent Variable: PERFORMANCE ORGANIZATION

The test results state:

1. First Hypothesis Testing
H2 : Community Trust affects Organizational Performance
2. Second Hypothesis Testing
H2 : Financial Organization affects Organizational Performance
3. Third Hypothesis Testing
H3: Leadership affects Organizational Performance

DISCUSSION

From the results of the above processing of each variable and the relationship between that the test between the variability of community trust and Organizational Performance has a significant influence, the third test with the results that financial organization has a significant influence on Organizational Performance, Leadership with Organizational Performance has a significant influence, and testing together found that 58.8% is significant and positive while the rest is influenced by other variables and not researched.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study produced findings of variable community trust with Organizational Performance there was a significant influence, the third test with the results that financial organization had a significant influence with Organizational Performance, Leadership with Organizational Performance there was a significant influence, and testing together found that 58.8% was significant and positive.

The results of this study are just the beginning and can be continued in other studies added with other variables with the same or other objects.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

The limitation of this study is only on examining the variables that exist on the topic in this study.

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